

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING INDEPENDENT CREATIVE THINKING OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *Strengthening of national independence and making a firm decision in Uzbekistan finally coincides with complex historical and socio-political situations. It is an even more complicated social problem to remove and cleanse citizens' minds, worldviews, and psyches from old-fashioned views, lack of initiative, stupidity, and addiction. At this level, in order to carry out large-scale and large-scale events in all aspects of society's life gradually, evenly, harmoniously and consistently, by educating young people who can meet the requirements of the new era, have a new consciousness and worldview, and who think freely, creatively and independently. cultivation is one of our most important tasks.*

Keywords: *education, training, thinking, student, creative, methodology, development, talented person, activity, activation of creative thinking, flexibility of thinking, communication, thought processes, modeling.*

Helping students to perform independent, creative activities means creating conditions for them to determine their positions and implement them in practice, providing tasks aimed at pedagogical support of their creative activities.

It is known that since the independence of our country, until today, a lot of scientific and practical work has been organized and put into practice to improve the quality and efficiency of education. It is important to prepare them as specialists capable of engaging in independent practical activities. The basis of the reforms carried out by our President Sh.Mirziyoev in the field of education is the importance of achieving high efficiency in education. Regarding the full implementation of reforms in the education system, it is necessary to be able to achieve a certain result through his independent thinking, creativity, and creative thinking during the training of personnel and the formation of creativity in them.

The content of our article is the recommendations of our research work on the development of students' ability to think independently, creativity, and creative thinking. This problem has been widely studied in the fields of higher school psychology, psychology of creativity, psychology of thinking, and the issue of formation and development of creative thinking in students has also been studied in the field of methodology of scientific creativity. Any person acquires a certain activity experience as a result of the development of professional knowledge. That's why a person should create, enrich and complete the experience of professional activity with his creativity. A student acquires such experiences in higher pedagogical educational institutions and enriches them throughout his life. A student should always be able to demonstrate important creative skills. Only then will he be able to show his creativity during his professional activity. Today, the person-oriented approach in teaching is one of the leading tools in the formation of creativity qualities in students: "self-management", "self-development", "personal activity", "self- The use of such concepts as "self-organization" in the practice of person-oriented education can also be the main evidence. The summarizing aspect of all this is that the subject himself is the initiator and organizer

of his own learning, education and development process, that is, the learner - student does not become a subject of knowledge, but first of all is counted as such.

The ability to think creatively in students is an expression of the abilities and skills, will, diligence and determination of a scientist, researcher, creator, and the ultimate goal is the desire to acquire new useful scientific knowledge. The object of our research is the types of thinking and creative activities of students of higher educational institutions.

The purpose of psychological study of students' readiness for creative activity or their creative approach to their future professions is the students' environment, the characteristics of their education, their ideas about scientific and artistic creativity, professional creativity and creative activity, the student community, The goal is to create favorable psychological conditions for the creative activity of a specialist-student. As a result of the step-by-step study of the dynamics of students' readiness for creative activity - the process of growth, specific aspects of students' creative thinking are revealed. Preparing students for a creative approach to their profession is a complex process that depends on the student's needs, values, emotions and intellect, as well as professional and life motivation. By forming creative thinking in students:

- the quality and efficiency of the integration of higher education and production will increase;
- we will increase the number of intellectuals, creators, competitive modern personnel in the society, and in this way we will increase the prestige of our society on the world scale;
- personnel competitiveness, level, labor and production efficiency, level of socio-economic stability in the society will increase.

This, in turn, will certainly serve the future socio-economic and political development of our society.

The results of pedagogical support of students' creative activities are manifested in the deepening of their individuality and creative qualities. Creative thinking, in turn, enables learners to:

- independent and conscious learning;
- always strive forward;
- reasonable resolution of various conflicting and problematic situations;
- teaches unconventional and new ways of thinking.

Creative activity is a form of thinking, which is developed by training ability, talent, desire, innovation, creativity are signs of creative activity. The main conclusion is that if the imagination of students about creative thinking expands, the motivation of their creative activity is understood, and special corrective methods for professional training are used, then the level of readiness for creative-creative thinking will increase consistently. Also, the effectiveness of students' scientific and creative research, support of talented students, science olympiads, student scientific conferences, and scientific and artistic circles also causes interest and motivation in creativity and the formation of relevant skills.

REFERENCES

1. Shamshetova A. Melibayeva R. va boshqalar. Umumiy psixologiya fanidan UMK,2016.
2. G'oziyev E.G'. Umumiy psixologiya. Darslik. -T.:O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati, 2010.
3. O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi (2000-2005yy)

4. R.N. Melibayeva, Tafakkurni rivojlantirishning interfaol usullari. Monografiya. “Adabiyot uchqunlari” nashriyoti, 2013-yil.
5. Akramova, D. (2022). Bo'lajak pedagog-psixologlarning maktabgacha ta'lim tizimidagi faoliyati. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 322-326.
6. Akramova, D. (2022). Oliy ta'lim muassalari talabalarida pedagogik-psixologik moslashuvchanlikni mazmun mohiyati. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 2150-2153.